

An Indirect Spectrophotometric Determination of Beryllium by Molybdenum Blue Method

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VARIOUS methods, i.e. spectrofluorimetry¹, atomic absorption spectrophotometry², gas chromatography³ and colorimetric⁴⁻⁷, have been reported for the determination of beryllium, but fluoride, phosphate, copper, cyanide, etc. interfere. In this communication a new indirect spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of beryllium which is free from the interference. The method is based on the precipitation of beryllium as beryllium ammonium phosphate in acidic medium. This precipitate is dissolved in hot dilute HNO₃ and treated with ammonium molybdate to form yellow heteropolymolybdophosphoric acid which on reduction with malonyldihydrazide (MDH) is converted to molybdenum blue. The method has been successfully applied for determining beryllium in spiked water, biological samples and standard beryl ore.

Experimental

A Varian 100 DMS spectrophotometer was used. A stock solution of 250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ beryllium was prepared by dissolving beryllium sulphate in demineralised water. Working standard was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure: Aliquots containing 0.1–0.8 ppm of beryllium were diluted to 10 ml and to which diammonium hydrogen phosphate (10%; 1 ml) and bromocresol green indicator (2–3 drops) were added. The solution was slightly acidified with 1 : 1 HCl till disappearance of the blue colour, kept in a water-bath and when hot, ammonium acetate was added dropwise till the colour changed to a distinct blue. It was kept in a water-bath for further 30 min till the precipitate became granular. The contents were allowed to cool and filtered. The precipitate was washed with 3–4 times with ammonium nitrate (2%) solution and then dissolved in hot dilute HNO₃ (1 : 4). The solution was evaporated on a hot plate to remove excess nitric acid and the residue was dissolved in 2 N sulphuric acid (5 ml). Then ammonium molybdate (10%; 1 ml) was added to it followed by 10 N H₂SO₄ (1 ml) and MDH solution (1 ml). The solution was kept on a boiling water-bath for 2 min, cooled and the volume was made upto 100 ml. The blue coloured solution was measured at 780 nm after 10 min against distilled water as the reference.

Results and Discussion

Maximum colour developed when the beryllium ammonium phosphate was dissolved in 5 ml of 2 N H₂SO₄ and 1 ml of 10% ammonium molybdate solution was added. The pH was maintained by H₂SO₄ at 1.5–2.0 during final colour development. At higher pH there was low absorbance values while at lower pH a high blank was observed. At least 2 ml of 0.1% MDH was required for complete reduction. There was no adverse effect on the colour formation at higher concentration on MDH. It required 20 min for complete precipitation and 30 min being sufficient for the precipitate to become granular. Colour development was complete after 10 min and the coloured dye was stable for 48 h.

Beer's law was obeyed in the range of 0.1–0.8 ppm of beryllium. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 9.46×10^3 (± 100) dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.00095 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.022 and 4.465% respectively for a solution containing 0.5 ppm of beryllium analysed over a period of 7 days.

To study the effect of foreign species various common interfering copollutants were added to 0.4 ppm of beryllium solution and the tolerance limit was as follows: K⁺, B³⁺, As, phosphate, chloride, bromide (400 ppm each); Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III}, Sn^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cr^{III} (300 ppm each); Al^{III}, Mg^{II}, Bi^{III}, Se^{IV}, nitrate, sulphate (200 ppm each); Cd^{II}, Ca^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, fluoride (150 ppm each). Iron, copper, nickel, phosphate, cyanide and aluminium did not interfere due to the selective complexing properties of EDTA.

Application: To assess the validity of the method it was applied for the determination of beryllium in river water, effluent water, tap water and biological samples spiked with known quantities of beryllium (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Be IN SPIKED WATER* AND BIOLOGICAL SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Sample	Be added ($\mu\text{g}/100 \text{ ml}$)	Be found** ($\mu\text{g}/100 \text{ ml}$)	% Recovery
1.	River water	20.00	19.50	97.50
		30.00	29.48	98.26
		60.00	59.47	99.11
2.	Effluent water (from steel industry)	20.00	19.60	98.00
		30.00	29.59	98.63
		40.00	39.83	99.57
3.	Tap water	10.00	9.95	99.50
		20.00	19.67	98.35
		30.00	29.83	99.43
4.	Blood	15.00	14.55	97.00
		30.00	29.78	99.26
		60.00	59.85	99.75
5.	Urine	20.00	19.78	98.50
		40.00	39.90	99.75
		60.00	59.86	99.76

*Samples were collected from different regions.

**Mean of three replicate analyses.

The method was actually applied for the determination of beryllium in beryl ore. The sample (0.1 g) was digested with HF–H₂SO₄–HNO₃ (12 : 4 : 1) for 1 h in a teflon bomb. It was then transferred into 1% boric acid solution, concentrated HNO₃ (5 ml) added and the volume made upto 250 ml. Aliquots of the digested sample were analysed by the proposed method and the reported method⁸. The recovery was found to be ~90% (Table 2).

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Be IN BERYL ORE*

Sl. no.	Present method		Reported method**	
	Be found μg	% Recovery	Be found μg	% Recovery
1.	22.0	90.0	22.2	98.80
2.	23.3	89.0	23.3	89.00
3.	22.8	91.2	22.7	90.80

*Amount of beryllium in standard solution = 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

**Ref. 8.

The method is found to be free from interference from most of the elements. In other colorimetric methods phosphate interferes while in this method it does not interfere. There was no prior separation as reported in many other methods^{4,5}. In most of the reported methods there were various interferences and the complex formed was unstable with a high blank.

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